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TEACHING VOCABULARY TO EFL CLASSES

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Abstract: This article includes information about effective ways and approaches to teach vocabulary to EFL classes. There are many vocabulary teaching methods which are important and useful for language teachers. Each method has its own role in language teaching process and the usage of these methods depends on teachers or instructors.

Key words: Approaches, context, technique, eliciting, memorizing, concrete word, abstract word.

Аннотация: Эта статья содержит информацию об эффективных способах и подходах к обучению лексике на занятиях по английскому языку. Есть много методов обучения словарному запасу, которые важны и полезны для учителей иностранных языков. Каждый метод играет свою роль в процессе обучения языку, и использование этих методов зависит от учителей или инструкторов.

Ключевые слова: Подходы, контекст, техника, выявление, запоминание, конкретное слово, абстрактное слово.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ingliz tili darslarida lug'atni o'qitishning samarali usullari va yondashuvlari haqida ma'lumot beradi. Chet tili o'qituvchilari

uchun muhim va foydali bo'lgan ko'plab lug'atni o'qitish usullari mavjud. Har bir usul tilni o'rganish jarayonida o'zining muhim rolini o'ynaydi va bu usullardan foydalanish o'qituvchiga va intruktorga bog'liq.

Kalit so'zlar: Yondashuvlar, kontekst, texnika, ma'lumotni jalb qilish, yodlash, aniq so'z, mavhum so'z.

Introduction. The usage of vocabulary is an essential component of any English language course. Many teachers are unsure how to teach vocabulary. New words must be introduced in such a way that they capture the students' attention and are remembered.

In order to progress in their language learning, students must be aware of techniques for memorizing large amounts of new vocabulary.

English vocabulary learning is frequently viewed as a time-consuming process of memorizing lists of unrelated terms. There are, however, many more effective and interesting ways to learn and teach vocabulary in the EFL classroom.

Words are the building blocks of a language, and as such, vocabulary acquisition is critical. Students can express themselves more fully and confidently as their vocabulary grows. Having a limited vocabulary, on the other hand, can have a negative impact on how students communicate.

Main part. Teaching vocabulary to **EFL (English as a Foreign Language)** students can be one of the most rewarding and challenging parts of language teaching. Effective vocabulary instruction goes beyond simply memorizing word lists — it helps students understand **meaning, use, pronunciation, spelling, and collocations** in context.

Teaching vocabulary should go beyond the use of common methods such as word searches, crossword puzzles, gap fills, and vocabulary journals in which students write definitions of new words. While these are useful, other approaches, such as contextual exposure to target vocabulary, can be more effective. Focusing on practice that requires students to use target vocabulary through productive skills such as speaking and writing is also beneficial. This promotes deeper and more long-term acquisition.

The main issue with vocabulary instruction is that only a few words and a small portion of what is required to know a word can be addressed at one time. This limitation also applies to incidental learning from listening or reading, but arranging for large amounts of independent listening and reading is much easier than arranging for large amounts of teaching. Teaching can only deal with a limited amount of information about a word at a time. The more complicated the information, the more likely it is that learners will misinterpret it.

There are some techniques which can be used for teaching vocabulary:

Anecdotes and gesture

Visuals and real objects are typically limited to concrete words and are likely ineffective when dealing with more abstract concepts and even some basic areas of vocabulary such as verbs, adverbs, and adjectives. These three areas of vocabulary, however, lend themselves to show mimes and anecdotes.

It is relatively simple to show gestures like jump and run, as well as distinguish between words that belong to the same group but have fundamentally different meanings, such as run, walk, stroll, sprint, jog, wander, and so on.

Realia and visuals

Showing students the word is one of the most effective ways of teaching vocabulary. Concrete words (mostly nouns) are typically showed through images or real objects. A word like table (as a noun) is simple to teach by pointing to one or showing a picture of one. Similarly, related words like board, coach, desk, deckchair, and so on can be taught in a similar manner, with the distinction between each made relatively clear. Even abstract words can often be conveyed using visuals; for example, the word happiness could be conveyed using a picture of laughter on the faces of people.

Translation

Another technique with advantages and disadvantages is translation. Many teachers and teacher educators regard translation negatively. They appear to believe that translation will keep the student from ever becoming proficient in the target language. This is obviously not the case. There are numerous examples of learners becoming quite proficient in a language despite heavily relying on translation. Translation is clearly advantageous in some situations. When a group of students shares the same mother tongue (and especially when the teacher does), it makes sense to use this facility on occasion. In fact, translation can frequently save time and aid comprehension.

Situations and explaining

Students' memories can be activated by eliciting words from them. Even at low levels, it is possible that one or two students in a class have heard the word before. It also allows you to determine how much your students already know. There are several methods for eliciting vocabulary, ranging from drawing a quick picture on the board to providing an explanation or a brief example of a situation.

When eliciting (or explaining) vocabulary, keep in mind that the language you use is simpler than the language you are attempting to elicit.

Using dictionaries

Giving your students learning strategies is an important part of teaching. Given the amount of time your students will spend outside of the classroom, it is obvious that you must assist them in becoming independent learners. Using a dictionary (especially a good monolingual dictionary like the Macmillan, Oxford Dictionaries) is one of the best and probably easiest ways to learn new words. Encouraging your students to use a dictionary in the classroom, for example, when reading a text, will be extremely beneficial to them. A good dictionary activity for developing vocabulary is to have your students look up a word they have recently learned and read the definition, then choose a word from the definition that they either don't understand or believe is important, and then look this word up and read the definition.

Conclusion. It is critical to understand that a good teacher will use a combination of these techniques rather than just one. Different techniques are appropriate for various vocabulary items as well as for various types of learners. As

you read through the various techniques, consider which words would be best taught using the technique and which would most likely not work well.

Vocabulary instruction is an essential component of any English language course. Many teachers are unsure how to teach vocabulary. New words must be introduced in such a way that they capture the students' attention and are remembered.

When English vocabulary is taught in an uninteresting manner, such as through drilling, simple repetition, and learning lists, the words are more likely to be forgotten.

Teachers must teach vocabulary in a memorable manner in order for the words to be retained in the student's long-term memory.

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